

Open Data Licenses

Data accessibility is defined by the presence of a user license. The license you select will determine the freedom with which others can reuse your data. When choosing a license, it is important that you adhere to any funder, repository, institutional, legal, or ethical obligations.

1 Data

CC0

Creative Commons Zero is ideal for openly sharing data – it has no restrictions on reuse whatsoever. While CC0 contains no requirement for attribution, citing CC0 datasets is widely accepted and expected in research.

Other CC licenses

If a CC0 license is not suitable for your data, consider the following CC licenses - all of which require attribution and further restrictions:

CC-BY Prevents others from applying legal restrictions beyond the terms of the license to the licensed dataset.

CC BY-SA Requires outputs derived from licensed dataset to also be licensed as CC BY-SA.

CC BY-NC Prevents the licensed data from being used for commercial purpose.

CC BY-ND Prevents the licensed data from being modified.

CC BY-NC-ND Prevents the licensed data from being used for commercial purposes or modified.

CC BY-NC-SA Prevents the licensed data from being used for commercial purposes, and requires outputs derived from licensed dataset to also be licensed as CC BY-SA.

Caution!

NC, ND and SA licenses have implications for reuse and interoperability. We suggest using a license that keeps your data as open as possible and as closed as necessary.

② Software

Making your software open source allows it to be freely used, modified, and shared by others. To ensure this is the case, you should consider using a license approved by the [Open Source Initiative](#). Popular OSI approved licenses include: [MIT](#), [GNU General Public License](#), and [Apache License 2.0](#).

Dual licensing

It is possible to license your software under both an open source license (typically GNU GPL) and a proprietary license. The restrictions on the reuse of your software will then depend on which license the software is distributed under. Dual licensing allows you to potentially profit from your software whilst maintaining the benefits of open source licensing.

③ Applying a license

Once you've selected a license, you need to apply it. Most licenses include application instructions, so it's best to follow these. Repositories also often support license application by allowing you to select a license from a pre-defined list on deposition.

Caution!

Be aware of any licensing restrictions where your dataset contains data derived from a third party.

Caution!

Licenses cannot normally be revoked, and license conditions may differ with version.

Toolbox

[OSI Approved Licenses](#)

[CC License Chooser](#)

[Choose an Open Source License](#)

[How to License Research Data](#)